

INCLUSIVENESS AND EQUALITY PLAN

HELIOS ACTION

CA22119 - Haemoglobinopathies in European Liaison of
Medicine and Science (HELIOS)

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1. INTRODUCTION TO HELIOS ACTION

The Haemoglobinopathies in European Liaison of Medicine and Science (HELIOS) Action is an Action funded by COST, the European Cooperation in Science and Technology¹, a funding organisation for research and innovation networks.

The HELIOS Action aims to build a network of excellence for integrating, harmonising and spreading the existing knowledge on haemoglobinopathies, including Sickle Cell Disease and thalassaemia syndromes. In addition, it intends to develop innovative services and tools, thus improving knowledge accessibility and healthcare equally across Europe and beyond.

HELIOS also contributes to the continuous training and capacity building, particularly for next generation scientists to effectively tackle recent challenges and potential treatment opportunities. This will allow to create a critical mass of highly skilled and trained researchers, who through mentoring from experienced scientists, will be able to foster and extend research in the field of haemoglobinopathies. To achieve its aims, the Action has brought together a diverse group of professionals from different disciplines (e.g., clinical research, laboratory genetics and molecular diagnosis, computational biology, bioethics, data management) and sectors (e.g., universities, research centres, healthcare centres, biobanks, private sector).

HELIOS comprises a well-structured governance, a Management Committee and five working groups. The five working groups coordinate existing and emerging haemoglobinopathy-related activities, ranging from clinical and molecular research to data analysis and bioinformatics, aiming to advance health care systems, contribute to informed policymaking and improve survival and quality of life for existing and future patients. According to the project proposal, HELIOS represented a balanced network with regards to seniority of the proposers and gender, as 41.6% of the proposers (32 in total) were Young Researchers and Innovators (YRIs), while 62.3% were women (48 in total). The Action seeks to expand among COST countries, International Partner Countries and Near Neighbour Countries, while respecting gender balance and promoting the active participation of young researchers and innovators. One of the objectives of the Action is to promote the participation of YRIs, women, and researchers from Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITCs) in leadership roles and throughout all project activities. Equality and inclusion principles will be promoted to fight any form of discrimination (such as sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation). More information about the project is available on the HELIOS website ([Home - HELIOS \(HELIOSaction.eu\)](https://www.heliosaction.eu)).

¹ <https://www.cost.eu/>

2. HELIOS ACTION - INCLUSIVENESS AND EQUALITY PLANS

In the context of the HELIOS Action, with the objective of adhering to the requirements set by the European Commission, Mrs Annalisa Landi, (Fondazione per la Ricerca Farmacologica Gianni Benzi - ETS, Italy) was appointed as Ethics, Gender Equality and Diversity Coordinator. Moreover, in March 2026, Professor Monika Nogel (Széchenyi István University Győr, Hungary) was selected as Co-Coordinator for the ethics and gender components of the Action.

In particular, the Ethics, Gender Equality and Diversity Coordinators must ensure gender balance in networking and training activities; inform about special opportunities for women in science and encourage candidates from ITCs, YRIs, and female scientists to apply for all management positions. In addition, they are in charge of guaranteeing compliance with applicable ethical standards and appropriately address any ethical issue arising during the project.

In order to promote an inclusive culture and to embed the need to mainstream a gender and inclusiveness dimension in all Action activities, Inclusiveness and Equality Plans are foreseen. The Plans aim to follow European guidance on gender equality and inclusiveness^{2,3} as well as to adhere to the COST Excellence and Inclusiveness Policy^{4,5}. These must be updated annually to allow information and details to be added or modified over time, thereby increasing their long-term impact. The first two plans of the Action were released respectively in April 2024 and April 2025.

2.1. HELIOS ACTION – THIRD INCLUSIVENESS AND EQUALITY PLAN

This plan represents the third one of the Action thus covering the period between April 2025 and March 2026. It aims to update the information about the gender and geographical distribution of HELIOS participants across leadership roles and working groups as well as to describe how the gender equality and inclusiveness actions and measures established in Y1 have been implemented in the Action following the calculation of the indicators. Moreover, the indicators have been revised, and two have been improved and reported as updated.

² https://commission.europa.eu/topics/equality-and-inclusion/equality-and-inclusion-key-actions_en

³ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/democracy-and-rights/gender-equality-research-and-innovation_en

⁴ <https://www.cost.eu/about/strategy/gender-equality/>

⁵ [Excellence & Inclusiveness | COST](#)

2.1.1. HELIOS ACTION - GENDER ANALYSIS

The first update of the state-of-play of the gender distribution within the HELIOS Action was performed by the Ethics, Gender Equality and Diversity Coordinator on the main subgroups (e.g., committees and working groups) part of the HELIOS Action considering the information as retrieved from the HELIOS Action COST webpage⁶. The third plan considered the data up to March 2026. The information was given by participants at the time of the application to the COST Action considering the COST classification (gender: male/female).

In detail, a total of 108 male and 146 females are involved in the Action. Moreover, out of the total of 254 HELIOS participants, the 44% (112/254) is represented by YRIs (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. HELIOS Action overview

Compared to the previous year, there has been an increase in membership, with 17.8% more male participants and 16.5% more female participants. The total number of HELIOS participants has risen from 217 to 254, corresponding to an overall increase of 37 participants (+17.1%). Interestingly, 73/112 YRIs are females. Finally, among the 146 participants coming from ITCs countries, 94 are females and

⁶ [Action CA22119 - COST](#)

69 are YRIs. An update of the gender distribution in the HELIOS Action by subgroups is shown in **Table 1** and in **Figure 2**.

Table 1. Overview of the gender distribution in the HELIOS Action by subgroups

<i>Tot</i>	140	137	130	145	102	36	21
<i>Male</i>	54	55	51	55	39	18	11
<i>Female</i>	86	82	79	90	63	18	10
	<i>WG1</i>	<i>WG2</i>	<i>WG3</i>	<i>WG4</i>	<i>WG5</i>	<i>Management Committee</i>	<i>Leadership roles</i>

Figure 2. Illustration of the gender distribution in the HELIOS Action by subgroups

Interestingly, during the reporting period, some changes were made to the leadership roles of the HELIOS Action leading to 11 males and 10 females covering these positions (**Figure 3**). In particular, additional co-leaders were appointed for some Working Groups (WGs) to strengthen coordination and support the implementation of activities while in other cases leadership roles were reassigned to new individuals.

Figure 3. Gender distribution in leadership roles

Figure 4 shows that the HELIOS Action Management Committee now has an equal number of male and female participants, following the addition of a new female member.

Figure 4. Gender distribution in the Management Committee

Finally, the gender distribution among WGs was updated to include changes over the three years of the Action. Interestingly, women continued to represent a higher percentage than men in all the Action's working groups. In detail, as per the last update, the WG1 consists of 54 males and 86 females (**Figure 5**), the WG2 consists of 55 males and 82 females (**Figure 6**), the WG3 consists of 51 males and 79 females (**Figure 7**), the WG4 consists of 55 males and 90 females (**Figure 8**) and the WG5 of 39 males and 63 females (**Figure 9**).

Figure 5. Gender distribution in WG1

Figure 6. Gender distribution in WG2

Figure 7. Gender distribution in WG3

Figure 8. Gender distribution in WG4

Figure 9. Gender distribution in WG5

2.1.2. HELIOS ACTION - GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRIBUTION ANALYSIS

An update of the geographical distribution of the HELIOS participants was carried out as well. Information as retrieved from the HELIOS Action COST webpage⁶ in March 2026 was used to perform the analysis.

The geographical distribution of participants in the Action shows continued diversity, with slight expansion compared to the previous reporting period. Most of the countries that were already involved in the Action have confirmed their participation, with several of them maintaining strong representation. In particular, Türkiye (31 participants), Cyprus (29), Italy (26), Greece and Albania (23) remain the most represented countries, indicating sustained engagement from key partners.

At the same time, the presence of new participating countries indicates that the consortium is continuing to grow with six new countries joining the action in year two and an additional country joining in year three (**Figure 10**). While these new participants currently contribute a limited number of representatives, their inclusion signals an ongoing effort to expand the network and increase its international reach.

Figure 10. Number of countries in the HELIOS Action per year

In line with the trend outlined in the previous reports, contributions from Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITCs) remain substantial (146/254 participants, 57%). Countries such as Turkey, Cyprus, Greece, Albania, Serbia and Slovakia collectively account for a significant proportion of participants. Additionally, participation from Near Neighbour Countries (NNCs), including Lebanon, Palestine, Egypt, Nigeria and Tanzania, has been maintained and expanded slightly, thereby further supporting the international dimension of the Action.

Overall, the data show continuity and gradual growth. While the core geographical distribution remains stable, the continuous inclusion of new countries demonstrates the ongoing commitment of the HELIOS Action to widening participation and fostering inclusiveness across regions.

An overview of the update of the geographical distribution of the HELIOS Action participants in total is shown in **Figures 11 and 12**

Figure 11. Geographical distribution of HELIOS participants per country

Figure 12. Map of HELIOS participants

Here below the geographical distribution of HELIOS members per subgroup as per the last update (Figures 13-19). In particular, **Figure 13** and **Figure 14** illustrate the geographical distribution of the **HELIOS leaders and members of the MC**, that changed recently, as stated above. Overall, the fact that members from 24 countries hold leadership roles in the Action highlights its commitment to the principle of inclusiveness.

Figures 13. Geographical distribution of HELIOS participants in Leadership positions

Figures 14. Geographical distribution of HELIOS participants in the Management Committee

The distribution of members in the 5 WGs shows similar trends with most participants coming from Cyprus and Italy followed by Turkey, Albania and Greece.

Figures 15. Geographical distribution of WG1 participants

Figures 16. Geographical distribution of WG2 participants

Figures 17. Geographical distribution of WG3 participants

Figures 18. Geographical distribution of WG4 participants

Figures 19. Geographical distribution of WG5 participants

2.1.3. HELIOS ACTION - ACTIONS & MEASURES ASSESSMENT (Y2)

The set of commitments and actions that aim to promote gender equality and inclusiveness principles, as identified in the first HELIOS Inclusiveness and Equality Plan, have been assessed now for the reporting period (April 2025-March 2026). The periodic assessment of the identified actions through the calculation of the related indicators helps identifying any possible gap or gender bias, implementing innovative strategies to correct any bias/gap, monitoring progress and improving the existing actions/measures.

The results of the assessment are included below.

1. General

OBJECTIVE	ACTION	INDICATOR	Y2	ASSESSMENT
Ensuring that the gender equality and inclusiveness principles are respected during the whole duration of the HELIOS Action	Appointment of a Gender Equality and Diversity Coordinator	GEP coordinator appointed	x	GEP co-coordinator appointed in March 2026 – Dr Monika Nogel
	Identification, update and analysis of relevant project data to prepare	Inclusiveness and Equality Plans annually updated, shared with	x	Second report released in April 2025 and published

	and share annual project Inclusiveness and Equality Plans Implementation of the plan actions and measures with the support of and in cooperation with leadership and executive bodies	the Consortium and uploaded on the project website Plan actions and measures implemented	x	on the website Actions and measures planned in the second report implemented
Promoting initiatives on gender equality and inclusiveness	To share with the Consortium of relevant news and material about past, current and planned initiatives that are relevant to the topics	Number of shared initiatives, material and news	x	6 initiatives, material and news shared
Investigating national policies and legislations of HELIOS partners on gender equality and inclusiveness	Analysis of national frameworks of HELIOS partners on the topics Informing the Consortium of the need to update institutional GEPs	Collection of relevant information, material and guidelines on the topics as well as national policies Information shared during the annual presentations on the topic	x NO	A dedicated WG was created resulting in the launch of a survey aiming to collect information from HELIOS members on institutional/ national policies To be done next year

2. Work-life balance and organisational culture

OBJECTIVE	ACTION	INDICATOR	Y2	ASSESSMENT
Ensuring an inclusive project environment	Creating an inclusive project environment by eliminating any form of discrimination during project activities and giving due recognition to the participation of women, ITCs researchers and YRIs	Number of alerts received by leadership bodies on forms of discrimination	x	No alert received
	Increasing the opportunity to take part in project meetings through the use of hybrid meetings	Number of hybrid/online meetings per year vs only in person meetings	x	>10 online meetings vs 3 in person meetings organised (working groups meetings excluded from the calculation)
Promoting and supporting work-life balance	Providing advice and support to HELIOS participants on work-life balance issues, if required	Number of support/advice requests received	x	No request received

3. Gender balance in leadership and decision-making

OBJECTIVE	ACTION	INDICATOR	Y2	ASSESSMENT
Promoting a gender balance in leadership and decision-making roles	Establishment of a gender-balanced composition of the board of directors and the management committee	Good balance in the number of males and females appointed in the HELIOS Action governance and management committee	x	47,6% of the leaders are females, 50% of the Management Committee members are females
Fostering the involvement of	Sharing relevant work opportunities as well as	Number of news and opportunities shared	x	No news shared besides the

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women in leadership roles	possible leadership roles for women	with the Consortium		opportunities for women to cover the new leadership positions open within the Action
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4. Gender equality and inclusiveness in recruitment and career progression

OBJECTIVE	ACTION	INDICATOR	Y2	ASSESSMENT
Ensuring gender equality and inclusiveness in working groups composition	Monitoring of the WGs composition. The WG leaders will consider the gender equality and inclusiveness principles during the selection procedures of new members	Balanced composition of working groups members	x	146 out of 254 members are females, great prevalence of women in the WGs composition, 146 participants coming from 16 ITCs countries, 112 members are YRIs

5. Integration of the gender and inclusiveness dimension into research and teaching content

OBJECTIVE	ACTION	INDICATOR	Y2	ASSESSMENT
Raising awareness on gender equality and diversity during training activities	Training sessions organised by the HELIOS Action Chair during annual meetings and/or dedicated slots during training schools	Number of male and female individuals targeted and reached by gender awareness-raising or planned training actions and related geographical distribution	x	Participants of the management committee meeting held in 03/2026: 15 females, 15 males coming from 18 countries of which 8 ITCs. Participants of the lecture on gender: 43 females, 16 males, with at least 15 individuals coming from ITCs.
Promoting initiatives to support gender equality and inclusiveness	Promotion of the participation of the Consortium in awareness days (e.g. International Women's	Number of initiatives communicated to the Consortium	x	2 initiatives communicated to the Consortium

	Day, International Day of Women in Science), through internal communications and sharing of news and relevant websites			
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6. Measures against gender-based or other forms of violence, including sexual harassment

OBJECTIVE	ACTION	INDICATOR	Y2	ASSESSMENT
Ensuring awareness of sexual harassment, of gender-based violence and any other form of violence and discrimination	Increase awareness about these topics during annual HELIOS meetings	Reference to the topics included in the annual presentation on the Inclusiveness and Equality Plan	x	Done during the lecture <i>Building Inclusive Organisations: Gender Equality Frameworks in the EU</i>

3. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the Action continues its commitment in promoting the principles of gender equality and inclusiveness and ensuring their implementation in all the activities of the Action.

This third HELIOS Inclusiveness and Equality Plan aims to report how actions have been implemented in the reporting period and how the principles of gender equality and inclusiveness have been guaranteed and confirmed by the Consortium. Moreover, it provides an update on the gender and geographical distribution of HELIOS participants across the leadership roles and working groups thus highlighting that the number of female participants involved in the Action remains high, while the number of YRIs keep increasing and as well as the number of countries joining HELIOS.

The periodic review of evidence and information as well as periodic assessment of the indicators identified continue to provide space for learning and feedback to enable adjustments and improvements to be made to the interventions.

Finally, as stated in the first HELIOS Plan, it is important to highlight that the implementation of the actions is also the responsibility of each member involved in the Action at all levels.